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GEO-STUDIES FORUM

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PLANT SPECIES FREQUENCY, ABUNDANCE AND FOREST DYNAMICS IN CENTRAL ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Global vegetation is experiencing a significant change due to disturbance of extreme climate events, natural hazards and human activities. Thus, it has contributed immensely to global tropical forest loss. The forest reserves in Central Adamawa State are gradually losing vegetation cover and have undergone profound changes in recent years thereby affecting the plant species structural composition of these forest reserves. Therefore, the aim of the study was to examine the pattern of plant species in Girei, Gurin, and Zangula forest reserves Adamawa State. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were applied in data collection. Descriptive statistic such as simple percentages, bar graphs and tables were used to analyze the data generated. The study revealed a regular distribution of high frequency (47.5%, 52.5% and 44.8% and 55.2%) and low abundance (9, 5, 5 and 3) for woody plant species; and non-woody plant species (24.5% and 65.7%) and (23 and 42) in the deforested area vegetation cover. Similarly, in the high dense forest vegetation cover species distribution pattern follows a patchy (contagious) distribution pattern with high abundance (11) and low percentage frequency (49%); while non-woody plant species follows a regular distribution (63.2%, 26%, 5.3 and 5%). Result further revealed the abundance class distribution of the total number of woody plant species rarely occurred (72.5%, 89.7% and 100%); non-woody plant species (92.1% & 7.9%; 75.3% & 14.3% and 76.3% & 10.6%). Conclude that the nature of the three forest reserves studied is homogeneous in nature as the number of woody plant species in A category is higher than the B category. Therefore, the study recommends an urgent need for government intervention to promote community-based and participatory approaches in forest management.*

Keywords: Plant Species, Frequency, Abundance, Forest Dynamics, Forest Reserve.

INTRODUCTION

All ecological systems share two important traits, structure and function. The structure of a system is defined by its measurable traits at a single point in time and can include living (biotic) and non-living (abiotic) components (e.g. plant height, plant morphology, and plant distribution). The functions of an ecological system involve the various processes that occur as the component parts exchange energy through time (e.g. oxygen consumption, biomass production, decomposition). The structural and functional processes have to be

quantified for thoroughly understanding the vegetation dynamics. The structural analysis of vegetation entails the floristic composition, stand density, basal area, vertical stratification and community types. While, the diversity provides information on species richness, distribution and rate of change in species composition (Adekunle, 2013), both structure and diversity of vegetation have strong functional role in controlling ecosystem process like biomass production, cycling of water and nutrients (Haruna *et al.*, 2018).

Forests constitute one of the principal renewable natural resources of mankind. They are essential in maintaining environmental stability, provision of raw materials for wood-based industries and provision of food, livelihood and employment for millions of people, particularly in the rural areas (FAO, 2024). It is worthy to note that in recent times, the concern has been to concentrate conservation effort on the tropical rainforest because of its relative richness in biodiversity. This rainforest consists of the moist tropical, and the lowland semi-deciduous forests, which form a narrow strip of green belt, a few kilometers inland along the Nigerian coast and covers a total area of 133,000 km² (Sanwo *et al.*, 2015). To protect forests from declining, it is essential to examine the current status of species diversity as it will provide guidance for the management of forest areas.

The Central Adamawa State Forest reserves are transitioning from dense Guinea-Savannah woodlands to fragmented grasslands. This shift is driven by a complex interplay of environmental stressors and human perturbation like high demand of land by nearby resident farmers, excessive and selective logging for fuelwood and charcoal, uncontrolled grazing and climate stress have led to the conversion of forest floors into farms leading to soil compaction and the destruction of the seedling bank and total loss of plant biomass. The dynamics of Central Adamawa State Forest reserves are currently characterized by an inverse "J-shape" distribution, which indicates a healthy potential for natural regeneration, with a higher number of small-girth trees (Hammanjoda *et al.*, 2025). However, factors like farming, fuelwood extraction, and grazing disrupt this stability. Studies show that 85% of local respondents have observed negative changes in species composition due to these activities (Hammanjoda *et al.*, 2025).

Information from this quantitative inventory will provide a valuable reference for forest assessment and improve our knowledge in identification of ecologically useful species as well as species of special concern. The present study will not only constitute a base material for the study area but will also be available for reference in future as the environment and ecology of the area degenerate as a result of its closeness to settlements. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the structure of plant species in Central Adamawa State Forest reserves Adamawa State by identifying the plant species frequency and plant species abundance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

THE STUDY AREA

Adamawa Central lies on the upper Benue between Latitude 08° 87" and Latitude 10° 68" North and Longitude 12° 38" and Longitude 13° 48" East (Figure 1). It covers a total land area of 16183.57 square kilometers (Zemba and Tukur, 2020). The selected forest reserves are located in the Northern Guinea Savanna and Sudan Savanna ecological zones of Nigeria, with a total land area of 217.48 square kilometers and they are all Gazetted (Akosim *et al.*, 2020). Central Adamawa area is like all other areas of typical tropical climate, experiencing generally high-temperature characteristics throughout the year. The temperature possesses seasonal change, indicating a gradual increase from January to April, where the temperature reaches its peak as high as 44°C, it decreases with the onset of the rainy season (Adebayo and Zemba, 2020). The area is characterized by two well-defined seasons, which are rainy (wet) and dry seasons. The average annual rainfall is about 972mm with an average of 62 rainy days (Ibid). The study area falls within the Northern Guinea and Sudan Savanna ecological zones of Nigeria characterized by short grasses, tall

and scattered tree vegetation, thick vegetation around hills and mountain ranges, and sparse short trees and shrubs (Akosim *et al.*, 2020). It is however necessary to note that large scale

deforestation resulting from indiscriminate extraction of wood for fuel and expansion of agricultural land have left large areas within each vegetation type with few indigenous wood plant species.

Figure 1: The Study Area

Source: GIS Laboratory Analysis, 2024

SAMPLING PROCEDURE AND DATA COLLECTION

There are different sampling schemes to use when collecting reference data. The combination of stratified and simple random sampling techniques was used to achieve the research objectives. Stratified Sampling technique was used to divide the forest reserves into strata, while simple random sampling technique was used to select sixteen (16) out of the thirty-two (32) subplots quadrants measuring 10m x 10m within each stratum to investigate vegetation structural composition.

Therefore, vegetation survey was conducted by dividing all the plant species into three classes, i.e., woody plant (tree) and non-woody plant (shrub, and herb). Woody individuals with a diameter at the breast height (DBH) $\geq 10\text{cm}$ were considered as trees, following Huang *et al.* (2018). Woody climbers were included in the shrub category and herbs are all plants with no woody stems. In the four corners and the center within each subplot, five quadrats of $1\text{m} \times 1\text{m}$ were established to investigate shrubs and herbs species (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Designed of the quadrats used in collecting Vegetation parameters
Source: Author’s Fieldwork, 2024

DATA ANALYSIS

SPECIES ABUNDANCE

According to Erry *et al.* (2017), if species are evaluated based on their density, called abundance by some researchers, the species are ranked as very rare, rare, occasional, abundant, and very abundant, and these ranks form relevant information to characterize the composition of the forest population.

A = Number of individual species equation 1

Source: Erry *et al.* (2017).

SPECIES RELATIVE ABUNDANCE

Species relative abundance refers to how common or rare a species is relative to other species in a defined location or community. Relative abundance can also be defined as the percent composition of a species of a particular kind relative to the total number of species in the area.

$$RA = \frac{\text{Abundance of respective species}}{\text{Total abundance of all species}} \times 100\% \text{ equation 2}$$

Source: Huang *et al.* (2018).

BASAL AREA

This involved determining the cross-sectional area of each tree trunk at 1.35 meters above the ground, measured in square meters. Thus, Basal area was determined based on the formula.

$$BA = \frac{\pi(C)}{4\pi} \text{ equation 3}$$

Where;

C = Girth size (Diameter at breast height)

Tree Girth: Stem diameter at breast height (DBH) is the measurement of the circumference of the tree taken at 1.3m above ground level.

Source: Huang *et al.* (2018).

SPECIES FREQUENCY

This is the percentage of incidence of a species in the set of sample units that were integrated into the floristic survey of a forest population. As suggested by Erry *et al.*, (2017), the frequency of a species is considered as the probability that it occurs in the forest population. If a species is found in all of the sample units, it will have a frequency of 100%. This method has been applied by Athua and Pabi., (2016); Erry *et al.*, (2017); Alanis-Rodriguez *et al.*, (2017); and Huang *et al.*, (2018).

$$F = \frac{\text{Number of quadrats in which species occurred}}{\text{Total number of quadrats studied}} \text{ equation 4}$$

Source: Erry *et al.* (2017).

SPECIES RELATIVE FREQUENCY

This is the ratio between the frequency of the *i*th species and the total frequency of

all species in the forest. Relative frequency (RF) is evaluated by taking the absolute frequencies of each species about the total frequencies of all of the species found in the sampling units taken in the forest population (Pereki *et al.*, 2013). For example, if 74 quadrats out of a total of 150 contain a given species the frequency is $74/150 \times 100 = 49\%$.

$$RF = \frac{\text{Frequency of occurrence of specie}}{\text{Total frequency of occurrence of all species}} \times 100\% \quad \text{equation 5}$$

Source: Pereki *et al.* (2013).

$$\% \text{ Frequency} = \frac{\text{No. of units in which the species occurred}}{\text{Total No. of units studied}} \times 100\% \quad \text{equation 6}$$

Source: Pereki *et al.* (2013).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FREQUENCY CLASS DISTRIBUTION OF WOODY PLANT SPECIES IN THE CENTRAL ADAMAWA

The distribution of woody plant species was evaluated by the ratio of species abundance

and percentage frequency described by Misra (1968) and Raunkiaer (1934). The result in the deforested area vegetation cover indicates that the distribution of woody plant species in Girei and Gurin forest reserves to have a regular distribution with high frequency (47.5%, 52.5% and 44.8% and 55.2%) and low abundance (9, 5, 5 and 3) indicating the species greater habitat adaptability of presence and grow (Table 1). In Zangula forest reserve the woody species indicated a patchy or contagious distribution having high abundance and low frequency percentage. This is in agreement with Haruna *et al.*, (2018) who reported 45%, 45%, 5% and 2% for frequency attributing it to the favourable micro habitat for the species. The patchy distribution reflects the presence of various micro habitat preferred by specific woody plant species under different terrain and substratum. In addition, the nature of the entire deforested area vegetation cover of the three-forest reserve studied is homogeneous in nature as the number of woody plant species in A category is higher than the B category. This implies that there is high diversity of species present but low in number indicating the level of degradation that have occurred in the forest reserves.

Table 1: Frequency Classes Distribution of Woody Plant Species in Central Adamawa

Frequency classes	Deforested Area Vegetation Cover						High Dense Forest Vegetation Cover					
	Girei Forest Reserve		Gurin Forest Reserve		Zangula Forest Reserve		Girei Forest Reserve		Gurin Forest Reserve		Zangula Forest Reserve	
	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species
A 1-20%	9	47.5	5	44.8	8	68.4	11	49	15	69	14	62.6
B 21-40%	5	52.5	3	55.2	2	31.6	5	51	4	31	4	37.4
C 41-60%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
D 61-80%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E 81-100%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The result further indicates that in the high dense forest vegetation cover in Girei forest reserve the species distribution pattern followed a patchy (contagious) distribution pattern with high abundance (11) and low percentage frequency (49%) (Table 1). This shows that the species are very common but occurred in small number either due to their economic value or cannot withstand the competition with other species in the area. This is in consonant with the work of Minakshi and Sumia (2017) where they reported similar pattern for Ferguson Collage Campus Pune India with high abundance of species (36) but low frequency (13.3%) (Table 1). The result further in contrast revealed that Gurin and Zangula forest reserves shows a regular distribution pattern with high percentage frequency (69% and 62.6%) for Gurin and Zangula forest reserves respectively. This implies that the species multiply in large number at the expense of other species.

ABUNDANCE CLASS DISTRIBUTION OF WOODY PLANT SPECIES IN THE CENTRAL ADAMAWA

The result of the abundance class distribution indicates that the percentage of the total number of woody plant species are rarely occurred in the deforested area vegetation cover of the three forest reserves with Girei (72.5%), Gurin (89.7%) and Zangula (100%) respectively (Table 2). This suggest that the species are being poached through selective harvest in the area. This is in contrast with Njoh *et al* (2023) who reported low species in rare and occasional category of Southwest Cameroun citing good reproductive capacity of the species and restriction impost by the government on human activities in the forest reserve. The result further revealed that it is only in Girei (27.5%) and Gurin (10.3%) forest reserves that some species are occasionally occurring either due to their high economic significance or level of preference by the wood/log harvesters.

Table 2: Abundance Classes Distribution of Woody Plant Species in Central Adamawa

Frequency classes	Deforested Area Vegetation Cover						High Dense Forest Vegetation Cover					
	Girei Forest Reserve		Gurin Forest Reserve		Zangula Forest Reserve		Girei Forest Reserve		Gurin Forest Reserve		Zangula Forest Reserve	
	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species	No. of species	% of total No. of species
Rare 1-4	11	72.5	7	89.7	10	100	14	85.7	14	78.2	18	100
Occasional 5-14	3	27.5	1	10.3	0	0	2	14.3	3	12.7	0	0
Frequent 15-29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	9.1	0	0
Abundant 30-90	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Abundant 100+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Furthermore, Girei forest reserve is homogeneous in which species in A category is higher than B category (Table 2). But, in contrast Gurin and Zangula forest reserves indicates a heterogeneous nature suggesting high species diversity in which the species percentage frequency of species in category B is higher than those species in category A.

The result further revealed that the percentage of the total number of woody plant species are rarely occurred in the high dense forest vegetation cover in Zangula forest reserve with (100%) species frequency (Table 2). This suggest that these species only occurred rarely as a result of level of degradation in the area. The result further revealed that the species are rarely and occasionally occurred in Girei (85% and 14.3%) and Gurin (76.2% and 12.7%) forest reserves respectively. This suggest that the level of degradation has not much impacted the reserves species richness and diversity. This agrees with Haruna *et al.*, (2018) who reported species abundance in the occasional and frequent categories (9, 10, 4,8 and 11) respectively in Kano Zoological Garden suggesting a low level of disturbance in the garden.

FREQUENCY CLASS DISTRIBUTION OF NON-WOODY PLANT SPECIES IN CENTRAL ADAMAWA

The result of frequency distribution of non-woody plant species in the deforested area vegetation cover revealed that in Girei forest reserve the species percentage frequency distribution revealed a regular distribution pattern with high percentage frequency (24.5% and 65.7%) and low abundance (23 and 42) indicating the species greater adaptability of disturbance (Figure 2). This agrees with Huang *et al.*, (2018) who reported high abundance and frequency percentage (4, 4.487%, 15, 18.071% and 8 9.63%) for Baturia Hadejia Wetland National Park Jigawa Nigeria. But, in Gurin and Zangula forest reserves the species indicates a patchy distributional pattern with high species abundance (1, 26 and 18) and low percentage frequency (0.7%, 51.6% and 47.7%) respectively (Figure 2). The nature of the entire deforested area vegetation cover of the three-forest reserves studied is homogeneous in nature as the number of woody plant species in A category is higher than the B category. This shows the lower diversity of species present and also occurred in low in number indicating the level of degradation that have occurred in the forest reserves.

Figure 2: Raunkiaer Percentage Frequency Distribution Class of Woody Plant Species in Central Adamawa

The result further revealed that in the high dense forest vegetation cover the percentage frequency distribution revealed a regular species distribution pattern in Girei forest reserve (63.2%, 26%, 5.3 and 5%) (Figure 3). But, in Gurin forest reserve the result revealed patchy species distribution pattern with high frequency and low abundance indicating the species greater habitat adaptability. Similarly, in Zangula forest reserve the species revealed a patchy (contiguous) distribution with high abundance and low percentage frequency of

occurrence. The patchy distribution reflects the presence of different species signifying the species richness of the vegetation cover. The ecological nature of the entire high dense forest vegetation cover of the three-forest reserves studied is heterogeneous in which the number of species in categories B, C and D is higher than those species than species in categories A and E. This implies higher diversity of species present occurring in large number in the non-vegetation cover of the three studied forest reserves (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Raunkiaer Percentage Frequency Distribution Class Non-woody Plant Species in Central Adamawa

ABUNDANCE CLASS DISTRIBUTION OF WOODY PLANT SPECIES IN THE CENTRAL ADAMAWA

The percentage of the total number of non-woody plant species are rarely and occasionally occurred in the deforested area vegetation cover of the three forest reserves with Girei (92.1% and 7.9%), Gurin (75.3%

and 14.3%) and Zangula (76.3% and 10.6%) respectively (Figure 4). This implies that the species are being tampered either through selective logging, uncontrol animal grazing or clearing for agricultural purposes. The result further revealed that it is only in Gurin (10.4%) and Zangula (13.1%) forest reserves that some species are frequently occurring in small number due to their high reproductive ability in the study area (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Raunkiaer Percentage Abundance Distribution Class of Woody Plant Species in Central Adamawa

The result further revealed that in the high dense forest vegetation cover the percentage abundance of the total number of non-woody plant species in the three studied forest reserves are rarely, occasional and frequently occurred for Girei forest reserve (82.2%, 9.5% and 8.3%), Gurin forest reserve (70.2%,

14.7% and 15.1%) and Zangula forest reserve (51.8%, 28.1% and 20.1%) respectively (Figure 5). This suggest that the three studied forest reserves have high species richness occurring in large number but experienced low level of disturbance (degradation) in the area (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Raunkiaer Percentage Abundance Distribution Class Non-woody Plant Species in Central Adamawa

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research has showed that parameters like frequency distribution and species abundance clearly portrayed that Girei, Gurin and Zangula forest reserves were under anthropogenic pressure and if the present trend continues, the reserves might lose its rich species diversity completely in recent times. These findings highlight the urgent need for the application of stricter laws to

deter people from encroaching the forest reserves to allow the rare species to regain their population restore and ensure sustainable management forest reserves. There is also an urgent need for government intervention to promote community-based forest management practices and integrate bottom-up and participatory approaches where all the stakeholders are involved in the process of rehabilitation and reforestation.

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